

Evaluation and analysis of psychological empowerment and their impact on organizational commitment

(Case study: Staff of Tax Administration of Sistan and Baluchestan)

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Abstract

Survival and life of any organization largely depend on the abilities, skills, knowledge and expertise of human resources; particularly its managers and whatever people are more knowledgeable, they could be better in improving the efficiency of organization. Now that all organizations are affected by rapid progress of technology in some ways, they must create changes in line with the progress in all aspects of their organization for maintaining and continuing their life. Foundation and starting point of all of this transformation is the empowerment and the proper use of human resources. So the goal of this research is the evaluation and analysis of psychological empowerment and their impact on organizational commitment (case study: Staff of Tax Administration of Sistan and Baluchestan). Research method is quantitative. Data collection is done by library and field studies. The results of this study indicate that there is a strong relationship between two main variables; it means that by increasing of employee's psychological empowerment of Tax Organization of Sistan and Baluchestan, We should see an increase in the level of commitment among employees of the organization.

Keywords: *psychological empowerment, organizational commitment, performance*

Introduction

Increasing of performance and efficient use of manpower is a necessity that should be considered by all managers and decision makers of organizations. Regarding that one of the most important resources within organizations is their personnel, a part of management actions with the aim of making the most effective and efficient work of these resources are implemented in this stage and effective management of performance has become one of the most important duties of directors. One of the impalpable factors affecting the performance of employees is their organizational commitment. Loyal manpower, consistent with the goals and values of the organization, is ready to be active even beyond the obligations set forth in the job description and can be an important factor for organizational effectiveness. Existing of such forces in organizations is coupled with higher levels of performance and lower rates of absenteeism and desertion and will cause that credit organizations in the community be seemed appropriate and provides the context for the development of organization. Conversely manpower with a low sense of loyalty, belonging and commitment not only does not move towards achieving the goals of the organization, but may have a negative impact on other partners by creating a sense of indifference to the problems and difficulties of organization and this provides the source of many abnormalities in various aspects of social, political, economic, social and cultural cooperation, so the study of organizational commitment and its influencing factors and the results can be an effective research in organizational behavior science. In the past decade, organizational commitment and its dimensions has allocated an important place in research. On the other hand, the power is the basic characteristics of a manager's role and provides the background of his effectiveness in the organization. In fact, it is an inevitable phenomenon in the organization but managers in organizations look at it as a negative phenomenon. But the truth is that this is not a negative phenomenon essentially, but also being positive and negative depends on the judgment and its application. Certainly, if the purpose of empowerment is the organizational goals, it can function as a positive phenomenon, and cause the system and organization be dynamics, but if the goal is to achieve personal goals, it certainly would be a negative and unaccepted phenomenon. Nowadays organizations are being changed rapidly and unpredictably and largely in environment. Increasing of global competition, development and deployment of information technology and changes in the demographic characteristics of human resources and customer are in the center of these changes (Bir and Jerilla, 1991, Benis and Nanos, 1985). In such circumstances, there is no opportunity for managers to control their employees and must spend most of their time and energy to identify the internal and external environment and charge other daily tasks to the employees. Therefore,

nowadays the most important source of competitive advantage for organizations is committed, motivated and conscientious employees (Bokhel, 1996). But, unfortunately their potential is often not used in organizations. For this reason, empowerment is considered as the most important challenges of managers in present time. As a result of these challenges, the managers must provide the conditions of organizations in a way in which each individual can be more powerful because a committed and competent workforce is one of the necessary conditions for effective functioning in modern organizations. Empowerment is a tool for giving a free hand to employees so that they can for what they think is best without the fear of not being approved by their directors and should have the freedom of action. Empowerment employee will be able to save the organization from crisis by using all aspects of empowering and will show their commitment and loyalty to organization by creating golden opportunities in business. Despite growing attention to empowerment, our understanding of this concept is limited and there is a little scientific study about the relationship of empowerment and the organizational variables in business area. One of the most important organizational variables that researchers and executives are interested in, is organizational commitment. There are few scientific studies that have studied the relationship of the effect of empowerment of employees and their organizational commitment although many writers and researchers have emphasized on the pivotal and the key role of organizational commitment in promoting and sustaining and performance of human resources (Kanungo and Kanngav, 1985; Kanungo, 1989; Dahrty and Denny, 1996).

The goal of the research

- Explaining of the role of psychological empowerment on organizational commitment
- Providing of job satisfaction of employees and reducing of their emotional anxieties

The hypothesis of the research

"Psychological empowerment of employees in organization effects on organizational commitment of employees"

Theories

Definitions and dimensions of organizational commitment

Among fans of attitude approach, some scholars see the organizational commitment as a multi-dimensional concept that affects different factors on it. Miers and et al are the pioneers of multidimensional approach, their Three-dimensional model of organizational commitment, including affective, continuous and normative dimension are as the three dimensions of organizational commitment.

Affective commitment

Alen and Mier believe that affective commitment is affective attachment to the organization and being identified through it. If we define the organizational commitment in this way, affective commitment will be involved in three dimensions:

- * The affective attachment to the organization
- * The willingness of the individual to determine his identity through the organization
- * And a desire to continue the organization's activities

Continuous commitment

The second dimension of Alen's and Meir's organizational dimensions is continuous commitment that is based on Biker's theory of investment (1960). According to this theory the individual accumulate some capital in organization over some time and the more the individual's record of service in organization the more the accumulation of his capital and its loss would be costly for the individual. These investments include the acquisition of particular skills that are not transferable and also include work friendship, political factors and other costs which deter the individual from searching for alternative works.

Normative commitment

The third dimension of organizational commitment which is less common, but it is questionable, is normative commitment that indicates a sense of duty to continue cooperation with the organization, those

with a high level of normative commitment feel that they must remain at the current organization (Allen and Meir, 1990).

About this dimension of organizational dimensions less research has been done than other dimensions, Randall and Kuti (1990), Allen and Meir and Avrili, Kaldvn Chatmn are the few researchers who have tried to separate this dimension of organizational commitment from other dimensions. Randall and Kuti (1990) have viewed the normative commitment from the perspective of a moral duty that a person feels through himself for investments that his organization has done on him.

The concept of empowerment

Many definitions of empowerment have been expressed. Most authors agree that the main element of empowerment is giving freedom to employees in activities related to their job (Conner, Patterson, 1992). The purpose of empowering employees is that they can develop all their skills and knowledge and use them for achieving their personal and organizational goals.

The dimensions of empowerment

Aspertizer focused on the psychological approach to develop a network of legal empowerment in the workplace. His model has been formed of four components that evaluate the employee's perception of significance, competence, effectiveness and determination. He defines the significant based on personal feeling toward the relations of between the work and personal standards. This sense will be created when the included tasks will be adapted with the values, beliefs and behaviors of individual. Sense of competence is the belief of the person in his ability to perform essential activities. Self-determination is self-perception towards his right choice about the work that he should do. The effects of feeling of a person about the amount of his influence on outcomes of a certain work (Abtahi and Absy, 200: 2005).

Conceptual framework of the research

The following model is a conceptual model used in this study. The model of "Aspertizer" is used to describe the independent variables (psychological empowerment) and the model of "Allen and Meir," is used to express the dependent variable (organizational commitment).

The research method

The purpose of the study is applicative and the method of data collection is descriptive and surveying. The statistical population of this research is all employees of the State Tax Administration of Sistan and Baluchestan which are 415 people and the numbers of samples of this research are 217 people. For collecting the field data, questionnaires have been used.

Reliability and Validity

The professors' and experts' views were used to study the validity of measurement. Also for assessing the reliability of the study, the criteria of Cronbakh's alpha was has been used.

$$r_{\alpha} = \frac{J}{J-1} \left[1 - \frac{\sum_{j=1}^J s_j^2}{s^2} \right]$$

Cronbakh's alpha coefficient of empowerment questionnaire $r_{\alpha} = 0/832$

Cronbakh's alpha coefficient of organizational commitment questionnaire $r_{\alpha} = 0/864$

Discussion and Conclusion

Ranking of component of psychological empowerment and their impact on organizational commitment

We study the ranking of component of psychological empowerment and their impact on organizational commitment at first and for the purpose; the stepwise Regression's test is used which the results are in the table below.

Table 1: Results of stepwise multivariate regression test to predict the organizational commitment

Sig	t	β	F	R^2_{Adj}	R	Variable	Step
0.000	14.81	0.729	219.57	0.528	0.729	competency	1
0.000	9.52 7.09	0.510 0.380	162.93	0.624	0.792	competency+ being effective	2
0.000	8.73 7.69 6.21	0.440 0.377 0.260	142.70	0.686	0.831	competency+ being effective + right of choice	3
0.000	8.46 7.90 4.55 2.01	0.426 0.386 0.215 0.094	109.75	0.690	0.835	competency+ being effective + right of choice + participation in information	4

The results show that among the components of psychological empowerment, four components have the greatest role in predicting organizational commitment. They are: a sense of competence, a sense of being effective, having the right of choice and participation in information. As shown in the above table, in the first step competency (predictor variable) was entered into the Regression equation, and predicts 52% of organizational commitment (criterion variables) and has had the greatest prediction of organizational commitment in the organization's tax affairs in the second step, the feeling of being effective has been entered into the Regression equation that with the components of competency have predicted over 62% of the changes in the criterion variable which the component of being effective, by itself, predicts 10% of changes in the criterion variable. In third step, the component of having right of choice has been entered the Regression equation which with two other components of organizational commitment have predicted 68% changes of organizational commitment, the component of having the right of choice, by itself, predicts 6% of changes of organizational commitment in Tax Organization. In the fourth and final step, the component of participation in information has been entered in the Regression equation that with the previous three components have predicted 69% of changes of criterion variable in which the component of participation, by itself, predicts 1% of changes of organizational commitment.

Testing of hypotheses

- * The employees' components of psychological empowerment have a significant effect on organizational commitment in the Tax Organization.
- * The model of Regression was analyzed in the form of the processing model for studying the amount of effect in which we will study it. In order to investigate and provide a model of psychological empowerment (Y) and organizational commitment (X), after reviewing the indices of the adequacy of the model which are written in following table, the processing model will be studied.

Table 2: Processing regression model between empowerment and commitment

The correlation coefficient	Coefficient of determination	The adjusted coefficient	SD error
.757	.573	.571	0.319

The correlation between the independent variables and the dependent variable is equal to 0.757. The coefficient of determination is 0.573 and this value indicates that 57.3% of the changes in psychological empowerment are related to organizational commitment. Since this amount does not account the degrees of freedom therefore, the adjusted coefficient of determination is used for this purpose which in this case is equal to 57.1%. Based on the criteria those were pointed, the model has enough efficiency.

Table (3): meaningful the regression by F test

Model	The sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	The mean sum of squares	F	Sig.
Regression	26.61	1	26.61	260.58	0.000
Remaining	19.81	194	0.102		
Total	4643	195			

According to the table above calculated level of significance for this statistic is equal to 0.000 and shows the significance of the Regression at the level of %99.0. The chart of Histograms drawn from the Regression model, has confirmed the normality of the data so the estimated linear regression model is accepted.

Figure (1). The histogram of the linear regression model

Table (4) Calculate the regression equation organizational commitment

Model		Non-standard coefficient		Standard coefficient	T	Sig
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Fixed amount	0.374	0.251	0.757	-1.488	0.000
	Empowerment	1.01	0.063		16.14	

Variables entered into the Regression equation is the core of Regression analysis which is listed in the table above. The regression equation can be calculated as follows by using the not standard coefficients column:

$$\text{Psychological empowerment (1.01) + 0.374} = \text{Organizational Commitment}$$

It can be said that by enhancing one unit of each independent variable to the extent of written coefficient, the dependent variable will enhance. Or in another word by enhancing one unit of empowerment, 1.01 of deviation units of organizational commitment will be enhanced. So as a result they have a positive relationship. T test for Regression coefficients for independent variables are also shown in the table. The value for this variable is equal to 0.000, so as a result it is effective in organizational commitment.

Conclusion

The main hypothesis of this study was verified and considering the value of the correlation coefficient, it can be said that there is a strong relationship between the two main variables, it means that by increasing of employees' psychological empowerment of Tax Organization of Sistan and Baluchestan, we should see an increase in the level of commitment among employees of the organization. The secondary hypotheses were also confirmed after the statistical tests.

So it is better that for increasing of organizational commitment in this organization, management attention should be given to all five dimensions of psychological empowerment. In the following of this study, in order to improve the level of commitment of tax affairs in Sistan and Baluchestan, practical suggestions will be offered. It is hoped that in this path, we shall see the increasing improvement and development of positive emotions of working and also we hope to see more organization's commitment of employees who the foundation of the economy is in their hands, to their job and the organization.

In the direction of implementing empowerment programs, the role of management is undeniable. In addition of empowering himself, the task of manager is to provide conditions to enable employees to empower themselves. Some of the conditions that provide fertile ground for the empowerment and the managers need to consider, are:

Managers with strategies and measures such as providing information, empowering, collaborative management, team building and giving independence to staffs, should provide the context required to perform administrative duties in such a way that the employees do what they want to do with interest and intrinsic motivation.

Since psychological empowerment is an internal and a private affair, which means that no one can empower a person unless he wants it to do, therefore, managers should play the role of facilitators and provide the conditions for the empowerment of employees by using of the techniques and strategies of managing.

Suggestions

1. For empowering of manpower, the programs of empowering can be implemented. Intellectuals of empowerment consider delegation, participative management and reward based on performance, as the programs of empowering.
2. Teaching of the technical and managerial skills in organization will enable the staffs to perform their activities more. Acquisition of appropriate skills through training programs causes decisions to be made of the highest quality and with minimal mistakes and properly.
3. Managers of the different parts should use the ideas presented by staff.
4. The organization can spend more time to review the requests of the staffs.
5. Appropriate incentive systems should be considered in order to enhance the capabilities of employees and improve their organizational commitment.
6. Management style should be led to participatory management, the management team and also to a flexible management.
7. Management should provide a clear definition of the staffs' responsibilities and authority.

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